

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СВЯЗЕЙ С ОБЩЕСТВЕННОСТЬЮ В ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОМ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТЕ

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Аннотация. В данной статье анализируются роль и значение связей с общественностью в политическом менеджменте. Связи с общественностью, по определению многих теоретиков, являются одной из ключевых функций управления в организации. В этой главе рассматриваются политические связи с общественностью. Во-первых, он характеризует политические связи с общественностью как центральный компонент политической коммуникации.

Ключевые слова: связи с общественностью, политическое лидерство, народ, общение, тактика, общество.

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF PUBLIC RELATIONS IN POLITICAL LEADERSHIP

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Abstract. This article analyzes the role and importance of public relations in political management. Public Relations, as defined by numerous theorists, are one of the key management functions within the organization. This chapter reflects on political public relations. It first characterizes political public relations as a central component of political communication by political actors.

Key words: public relations, political leadership, people, communication, tactic, society.

Public Relations in politics is only public exposure of brands or famous people it is wrong to interpret it as giving. Specialist in public relations as you can think hard, think along the way, your emotions you will have to watch and respond carefully. Otherwise disadvantaging the company or organization you represent you can put. It is known from world experience that if the subject of political administration is in crisis the best way is to use effective PR tactics. PR tactics are especially effective in social networks.

In Uzbekistan, public relations and communication with the people are becoming an important social institution. It is proven in life that public opinion is a wonderful mirror that reflects the civil society. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in his greetings to the employees of the field on June 27, 2017 - the Day of Press and Mass Media Workers, "Communication with the people, living with people's dreams, aspirations, pains and worries is rising to the level of state policy. We will be able to achieve our goals only if a mass media becomes a platform for real communication, a forum for free opinion [1].

On June 28, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Public information ensuring the independence of means and information of state bodies and organizations on

additional measures for the development of services Decision No. PF-4366 was adopted. Now the heads of information services Certification from mass media has been set. Also information with media representatives on the service side, including state and economic administration regularly (at least once a month) with the participation of the heads of the bodies holding of press conferences, briefings and mass media and implementation of other modern forms of working with the public was defined as mandatory.

Social networks communicate with a political party or leader is an ideal tool for creating conversations. The political party has its memoranda and live streaming of press releases on platforms such as YouTube possible, But too much media information through social networks distribution can backfire. Public relations working for a candidate or party organization. As an expert on social media, you have been published on social media platforms you should carefully monitor the contents.

In politics, the purpose of PR is in relation to other subsystems in society is to provide features, themes and programs. In fact, it is attention and interest involvement, as well as their positions, interests and key players including raising awareness and image profile. PR in politics used to convey information and form political opinion. Mutual understanding and interests of PR professionals with key target groups constant communication to create and promote a favorable environment for the agreement should do.

Since one of the main tasks of the information service is to develop the organization's relations with the public, special attention is paid to the issues of ensuring public and parliamentary control over the activities of the state authorities and management bodies of the mass media, establishing strong relations between the state and the public. . In our country, extensive work is being done to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for the mass media to operate effectively, to implement the rights of citizens to receive and use information freely and without hindrance, to protect information, and to ensure the information security of individuals, society and the state. In the process of consistent reforms in the field, information services are being established in state power and management bodies, all ministries and agencies, and public organizations, and their activities are being implemented based on the needs of the times.

Studying the opinion of the public is an important criterion in relations with it. In practice, the term "function" refers to tasks that perform this activity. According to V. Korolko, public relations generally performs 3 main functions. Studying public opinion and observing it. Through PR, it is possible to study public opinion and effectively influence it only in this way. If the public opinion is not studied in time, then the positive goal will not be achieved [2].

Monitoring public behavior. Therefore, it is important not only to study the opinion of the public, but also to monitor its actions. It should find out how he behaves in this or that public action. As new situations arise, as social moods change, it is necessary to know in advance how the public is behaving, and in which direction the public opinion is changing. Accuracy plays an important role in the work of a PR employee.

Ensuring mutual benefit between the organization and the public. It is necessary to develop cooperation with the public by ensuring not one-sided, but two-way interests. In this case, cooperation will have a double benefit.

PR serves to establish public relations of organizations in the society. As Sam Black writes, it is directed to the following ten main goals. That is:

1. Public opinion;
2. Public relations;

3. Intergovernmental relations;
4. Social life;
5. Industrial relations;
6. Financial relations;
7. International relations;
8. Relations with consumers;
9. Statistics and research;
10. Media.

The most important shortcoming within the field of political public relations research is that most public relations theories and concepts have seldom or never been applied in the context of political public relations. To do so, and extend political public relations to domains seldom investigated, should be the most important priorities in future research on political public relations. Not only would it increase our understanding of political public relations per se; it would also test the validity of public relations theories beyond traditional contexts. For example, rather limited attention has been given to the role of non-profit organizations, activism, government communication, and fundraising in political public relations. Although left out from this chapter for reasons of space, we believe these are fruitful arenas for future scholarship. We also believe that theories such as, for example, excellence theory, contingency theory, situational theory, and relationship management theory have much more to offer in the context of political public relations, and needs to be explored and tested in political contexts.

Today's world is a world of communication and in every second, millions of information units are exchanged in the world. Since development of human life improves, thus increase need to information and communication every day increased and nowadays having accurate and up to date information for people is the important and people with more information will be more successful. In public organizations have reliable information, accurate and timely, considering the purpose and structure is an organization's greatest asset and survival of an organization depends on having a reciprocal relationship between internal and external of organization and advertising, and up to date and useful information and appears necessity of the real public relations in public affairs station. In today's world that has broken communication boundaries and human seek to discovery of optimal solutions life and attitude of the society oriented. Scientific principles lead to explore and focus on the interaction conditions and to involve. Undoubtedly, an organization, or an agency cannot be considered unrelated to their island and no need and unrelated from technology and its products [3]. Public relations should be based on thinking oriented, collaboration oriented and information-oriented in order to effectively contribute to the effectiveness of the organization and with innovation and modernity, originality and creativity is continually involved and coincide themselves with developments and responding regularly to public opinion.

In conclusion, PR services in organizations in recent years became much more active. It started communicating with people. Response to criticism reporting has become a habit. This is a very happy situation, of course. However, the organization and initiative in forming a positive image of the leader is not always supported. All middle and lower level managers to the public the desire to open up, to have a bright image of themselves in society are not reported. Therefore, retraining and upgrading of PR services does not give the expected result. The same tendency in the middle and lower ranks Creating an enabling environment is the government's next priority one of the tasks.

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